

Deep Learning in GeoSpatial Artificial Intelligence.

Geospatial artificial intelligence sometimes referred to as geoAI is recently receiving so much attention. From large-scale projects to smaller projects. GeoAI can be referred to as using artificial intelligence with Geographical information system to analyse and produce solution-based predictions.

GeoAI is improving geospatial diversity in a lot of ways. With a case study such as predicting particulate matter air pollution in Los Angeles, geo AI has used openStreetMap to improve the prediction between roads pollution with other human efforts based on time, past behavioral pattern and particle concentration. This help to intelligently forecast dangerous levels of air pollution level before it gets out of hand. The application of Geospatial AI is endless as it affects, resource allocation, improvise planning and decision making with regards to supply chain efficiency.

Deep Learning and Mapping.

One of the major problems we face is how to understand large data-set and model it. This challenges affect several aspect of Geospatial GIS including geophysical monitoring, pattern recognition, events monitoring and so on. Machine learning including Artificial Neural Networks somethings referred to as Deep learning and Support Vector Machines (SVM) are very essential for intelligent geo-and environmental data analysis and visualization.

Deep learning is an aspect of machine learning that goes further in processing large data-set with more accuracy. In the past, differentiating textual information such as map features, names of places, contours through automated map readers has been very difficult. Deep learning through the development of optical character recognition allows map readers to interpret different variation of information such as text and graphics.

For remote sensing on large datasets, it is very possible to turn raw photon readings into sensible measurements that helps decision making. Satellite imagery can now be very accessible on cloud native geospatial infrastructures which is very

effective with tremendous data warehouse. Today Google's Cloud Vision API uses deep learning for image recognition with great precision.

Deep learning is an analytical approach that combines different layers responsible for analyzing different aspects of colors, image, circles, faces etc. When this algorithm is exposed to this abundant images, they are trained to identify and classify new images as against what has been previously seen. This results to a model that has been trained on many images and classified. It is important to note that, to achieve greater accuracy one should apply different statistics/ geo-statistical tools required to improve the outcomes of the quality of the data analysis and modelling.

Geospatial Data Analysis Tasks

There are 3 tasks of statistical learning from data which is referred to as classification, regression and probability density modelling. We understand that machine learning are universal tools meaning that it can model any mapping be it continuous data or categorical data with great precision. It is important while designing a model to select a good structure of the machine for instance multilayer perceptron and how its parameter is tuned. There are several approaches to hyper parameters tuning such as cross-validation, splitting of data etc. For geospatial data geostatistical tools, variography can be very useful tool to control the parameters and procedures tuning.

Let's examine some typical geospatial data analysis problems and corresponding methods in solving them

- Multivariate joint predictions of several variables: geostatistics (co-kriging), machine learning (multi-task learning).
- Risk mapping – modelling of local probability density function: geostatistics (indicator kriging, simulations), machine learning (Mixture Density Networks).
- Optimization of monitoring networks (spatial sampling design/redesign): space filling models, geostatistics (kriging, simulations), machine learning (Support Vector Machines). The basic idea of using Support Vector Machines for spatial sampling

design is that only support vectors are important measurement points contributing to the solution of mapping problem

- Modelling of spatial variability and uncertainty, conditional simulations (spatial Monte Carlo simulations): geostatistical conditional stochastic simulations (sequential Gaussian simulations, indicator simulations, etc.).
- Spatial interpolations. Spatial predictions in a high dimensional geo-feature space – machine learning, deterministic interpolators, geostatistics, machine learning
- Data mining in a high dimensional geo-feature space: machine learning (supervised and unsupervised learning algorithms).

Applications of geospatial AI through deep learning.

1. Internet of Things- (IoT)-

Deep learning models has increasingly been very useful in GIS application software using neural platforms to predict, learn, adapt and make recommendations for end-users. Neural Geospatial data systems has become a fundamental foundation for self-driving cars. Also, Drones have been designed to adapt through a real-time environment using different kinds of GIS data.

2. Predictions and remote monitoring-

Deep learning systems are able to analyze complex weather and climate imagery data that would have originally taken so much time and resources. It can carry out real-time forecasting of issues using geospatial data concerning air pollution, climate change, water pollution and agriculture data.

3. Consumer behavior in a geography.

The need to understand the consumer patterns of end-users has become a key to the sustainability of any organization. Today, deep learning models help to learn and predict the behavior of consumers using geographic data. Neural

based systems can solve regional demands by creating an ecosystem based solution using various GIS analytics.

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